

Annex A – Analysis Framework

Name of organisation

Year the report refers to

- Academic year 2019-2020
- Academic year 2020-2021
- Academic year 2021-2022
- Calendar year 2019
- Calendar year 2020
- Calendar year 2021
- Calendar year 2022

Date statement approved by governing body

- Date available
- Statement approved by governing body but no date available
- No information on statement approval by governing body

Date statement approved by governing body

Web address of organisation's research integrity page (if applicable)

Named senior member of staff to oversee research integrity

- Name
- Personal email address (i.e. belonging to the named individual)
- Generic email (not named)
- No contact information available
- Job role is research integrity specific
- Job role is NOT research integrity specific
- No job role information

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Named member of staff who will act as a first point of contact for anyone wanting more information on matters of research integrity.

- Name
- Personal email address (i.e., belonging to the named individual)
- Generic email (not named)
- No contact information available
- Job role is research integrity specific
- Job role is NOT research integrity specific
- No job role information

Promoting high standards of research integrity and positive research culture. High-level questions

- Statement to provide assurance that the processes the institution has in place for dealing with allegations of misconduct are transparent and timely and robust and fair.
- Statement to provide assurance that the processes the institution has in place for dealing with allegations of misconduct continue to be appropriate to the needs of the organisation.
- High-level statement on any formal investigations of research misconduct that have been undertaken.
- Information on how the organisation creates and embeds a research environment in which all staff and researchers and students feel comfortable to report instances of misconduct.
- Information on any indicators of research integrity that the institution may be using internally (e.g., number of X reported; percentage of Y reported)
- Information on any networks of which the organisation is a member (e.g., UK Reproducibility Network - UKRN; UK Research Integrity Office - UKRIO; UK Council for Graduate Education - UKCGE; any research integrity network- e.g., SRIN; any mission group integrity network - e.g., Russell Group Research Integrity Forum)
- Commitment to support a research environment underpinned by a culture of integrity; good governance; best practice.
- None of the above

CURRENT systems and culture, General

- Policies
- Procedures and practices
- Communications and engagement
- Culture and leadership
- Monitoring and reporting
- Support or training provided to researchers
- None of the above

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CURRENT systems and culture, Training provision

- Examples of support or training provision for individuals at different career stages
- Examples of support or training provision in different or across disciplines
- Examples of support or training provision with an EDI focus
- Examples of mentoring opportunities for researchers
- Examples of support or training provision on research culture
- None of the above

Which of the following (if any) are NEW or have been UPDATED in the period considered by the annual report?

- New or updated Policies
- New or updated Procedures and practices
- New or updated Communications and engagement
- New or updated Culture and leadership
- New or updated Monitoring and reporting
- New or updated Support or training provided to researchers.
- None of the above

Does the report include any of the following?

- Reflection on the previous year's activity including a review of progress and impact of initiatives.
- Information on formal evaluations of research integrity provision carried out in a relevant period
- Plans for future development arising from reflections (e.g., evaluations) on the previous year's activity.
- Issues that have hindered progress such as resourcing or other issues.
- None of the above

Does the report include any CASE STUDIES or SUCCESS STORIES that might be valuable to other organisations?

- Case study on Policies
- Case study on Procedures and practices
- Case study on Communications and engagement
- Case study on Culture and leadership
- Case study on Monitoring and reporting
- Case study on Support or training provided to researchers.
- Case study on Something else
- None of the above

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Addressing research misconduct. Does the report include any of the following information around systems, processes and policies with regard to research misconduct?

- Confidential pathways or safe spaces for people wishing to raise concerns (e.g., misconduct; methodological practice; errors)
- Periodic review and evaluation of the organisational approach to misconduct (e.g., date of last review; any major changes during the period under review; date when processes will next be reviewed)
- Lessons learned and opportunities for improvement identified after allegations or investigations.
- Breakdown of misconduct cases by a given grouping (e.g., by staff type; by discipline; by location/site)
- None of the above

Does the report mention documents covering any of the following?

- Bullying and harassment policy/procedure
- Whistle-blowing policy/procedure
- Misconduct policy/procedure
- Ethical approval policy/procedure
- Code of practice for research
- Research data management policy
- Open research / Open access / Open data policy
- Trusted research
- None of the above

Did the organisation provide information on allegations and investigations?

- Yes, and figures have been captured.
- Yes, but there were no allegations or investigations.
- No information available on allegations or investigations

Total allegations and investigations

TOTAL allegations reported

TOTAL allegations formally investigated

TOTAL allegations upheld in part

TOTAL allegations upheld in full

Allegations and investigations by type

Fabrication - Allegations reported

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Fabrication - Allegations formally investigated

Fabrication - Allegations upheld in part

Fabrication - Allegations upheld in full

Falsification - Allegations reported

Falsification - Allegations formally investigated

Falsification - Allegations upheld in part

Falsification - Allegations upheld in full

Plagiarism - Allegations reported

Plagiarism - Allegations formally investigated

Plagiarism - Allegations upheld in part

Plagiarism - Allegations upheld in full

Failure to meet legal, ethical and professional obligations - Allegations reported

Failure to meet legal, ethical and professional obligations - Allegations formally investigated

Failure to meet legal, ethical and professional obligations - Allegations upheld in part

Failure to meet legal, ethical and professional obligations - Allegations upheld in full

Misrepresentation - Allegations reported

Misrepresentation - Allegations formally investigated

Misrepresentation - Allegations upheld in part

Misrepresentation - Allegations upheld in full

Improper dealing with allegations of misconduct - Allegations reported

Improper dealing with allegations of misconduct - Allegations formally investigated

Improper dealing with allegations of misconduct - Allegations upheld in part

Improper dealing with allegations of misconduct - Allegations upheld in full

Multiple areas of concern (when received in a single allegation) - Allegations reported

Multiple areas of concern (when received in a single allegation) - Allegations formally investigated

Multiple areas of concern (when received in a single allegation) - Allegations upheld in part

Multiple areas of concern (when received in a single allegation) - Allegations upheld in full

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Other - Allegations reported

Other - Allegations formally investigated

Other - Allegations upheld in part

Other - Allegations upheld in full

If there are any listed allegations under the 'Other' category, is there a brief, high-level summary of their type?

Yes

No